

Analyzing the Level of Instruction among Students, Teachers and Administrators in Higher Educational Institutions and the Competitiveness of Hospitality and Tourism Facilities: A Literature Review

Carenh M. Abenaza
Hotel and Tourism Manage
Department, Cebu Roosevelt
Memorial Colleges, San Vicente St.,
Bogo city Philippines, 6010

James H. Samillano
College of Teacher Education,
Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges,
San Vicente St., Bogo city
Philippines, 6010

Ariel O. Tinapay
Graduate School of Education,
Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges,
San Vicente St., Bogo city
Philippines, 6010

Abstract:- This study focused on determining the competitiveness of facilities' and level of instructions' among students, teachers and administrators in HEI in Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges. The literature findings of current study benefit the skill development of students and teachers for effective performance as well as the knowledge to commit itself to the development of highly competent successful professionals as they are provided by the school administrators with opportunities to analyze the current analysis of learners and teaching methods towards the curriculum. The study aims to determine hospitality and tourism management courses contributes with students' competitiveness from the quality of the facility and effectiveness of the instructions along the support of the administrations. The key themes presented in this work are the following: Assess the efficiency of the hotel and tourism school's curriculum based on student perceptions of readiness, identify the easiness of performance of facilities' that can be used by teachers and students, identify areas of knowledge and expertise wherein hospitality teachers and learners are more and less able to prepare, and factors affecting administrators. The concepts presented have been embedded into the literature review and related studies

Keywords:- Administrators, Competitiveness, Higher Educational Institutions, Hospitality and Tourism Facilities, Students, Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The review of literature begins with an analysis of the two variables of facilities and instructions, of their indicators, and how they relate to an individual's perspective and awareness. The literature reviews are also present of the significance of the facilities' competitiveness and instructions competitiveness that may affect the quality and effectivity. A review of related literature and studies on the quality theory, competitiveness advantage theory, and humanism theory learning from the different gurus. The review concludes with a discussion of the Total Quality Management Theory, Competitive Advantage Theory, and Humanism Learning Theory. TQM theory is a study of

qualities in which business engages to ensure products meet customer needs.

Quality Management is a systematic approach to managing an organization's overall operations. The process's goal is to continuously improve internal practices in order to increase the quality of an institution's outputs, including services and products. The standards established as a component of the Company framework can highlight all these internal priorities and existing industry standards. Competitive Advantage theory study of factors conditions for productivity growth of strategic management. This refers to the factors or characteristics that distinguish one company from its competitors in terms of producing more affordably priced or better quality services or products. It refers to the factors that allow a company to create products or services better or at a lower cost than competitors, resulting in much more selling or greater profit margins. Humanism Learning theory studies central assumptions of humans, is that people act intentionally and values which cognitive psychologist believes that constructing meaning or discovering knowledge is central to learning. Humanism underlines the freedom of individuals to behave and govern their own destinies.

It is concerned with human values, interests, capabilities, wants, worth, and dignity. It is the belief that individuals have an infinite capacity for growth and improvement and they are intrinsically good. Learning is the process of gaining new knowledge, personality traits, skills, and virtues through research, practice, and/or experience. It is a "process by which behavior is changed, shaped, or controlled".

II. LITERATURE DISCUSSIONS AND REVIEW

A. School Facilities

In an educational institution, facilities are a part of the property which enables students achieve their goals. The purpose of the educational organization facilities is to provide students with a comfortable learning environment. Higher education infrastructures are physical goods and facilities that directly contribute to the efficiency of teaching and learning in the education systems. This will provide the institutions with the right condition and ambience for learning and teaching. Higher education

facility development is incredibly difficult in order to guarantee high-quality instruction and maintain global standards. Buildings, classrooms, workshops, laboratories, and a tour and travel bureau are all part of the development. Inadequate facilities have a substantial impact on students' learning and teachers' attitudes toward classroom activities. (Abdullahi, Wan, & Wan, 2018).

Facilities are vital for bringing in new students and providing learning environments (Price, et al., 2003). High-quality and standard facilities are perceived to have a strong influence on students' selection of an institution of higher learning (Price et al., 2003; Douglas et al., 2006); on participants' educational process (Lewis, 2000); as well as on general impression of the school (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001), and it differentiates universities from their competitors. As an outcome, university facilities are viewed as one of the most key strategic sources for gaining a competitive edge in the sector of higher education (Weerasinghe, Fernando, & Roberts, 2018).

Physical facilities include school buildings, classrooms, libraries, laboratories, offices, and other components and infrastructures that are likely to motivate students to learn. The physical resources supplied for teachers, staff, and students to maximize productivity in the process of education and learning are referred to as school physical facilities. This is to provide and maintaining a safe, tidy, and innovative educational environments that encourage students to achieve high levels of success. Physical premises strive to provide students with a comfortable environment in which to work and learn. The facilities' are important for students' efficient learning and academic achievement. All must be made available to schools so that students can have more concrete and real-world experiences. The availability of learning resources and materials, as the dominant reason in contributing to educational excellence in the school system, are critical factors in students' better learning and achievement and for suitability and easiness of the subject taught (Lyimo, Too, & Kipng'etich, 2017).

B. Quality of School Facilities

Quality indicators can be the foundation for a variety of academic involving judgements, distinctions (through the advancement of a ranking model), assurance, and operational and strategic planning in hospitality and tourism programs. Quality assurance and a total quality management system through tourism and hospitality education services depending on the recommended quality indicators would help to elevate local offerings to exhibits high standards. When choosing a degree, potential students and their family members will have direct exposure to an impartial decision-making tool. (Anastasios, et. al., 2014).

The post-occupancy evaluation (POE) technique was employed to evaluate the quality of HEI facilities which reflects common components referred to as CIPP, MBNQA, and other quality system. The performance of any business isto provide a secure and productive working environment. It is to operate effectively and efficiently and offer better levels of client satisfaction through improving

current facility quality to enhance the functional ability and image of a facility and its systems. Meanwhile, unless this is integrated into the HEI's marketing strategy, it must be assumed that the facility's quality will have no effect on student choice. As a result of changes in the educational sector, learning and teaching strategies, and user expectations, the connection between both the value and quality of higher learning institutions can be viewed as a dynamic relationship (Vidalakis, Sun, & Papa, 2013) .

C. The Efficiency of School Facilities

Efficiency measures how well a company uses its resources to achieve the best results over time. Efficiency is split into two components allocative efficiency and technical efficiency. The first is an organization's ability to use varying assets in ideal dimensions to generate a mix of various outputs while taking input costs and production technology into account. The other involves the physical correlation between the consumed resources, such as equity, labor, and equipment, as well as achieving the highest output level with the fewest obtainable sets of inputs. Total efficiency is measured in general by the cumulative effect of allocative and technical efficiency. This type of analysis enables a better understanding as to how efficient and effective service delivery components work of the resources in the facility (Babalola & Moodley, 2020).

Philippine Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs) must dwell on core functions, establish closer ties to economy, collaborate with both local and international communities, and promote greater operational efficiency. They entail trying to manage the whole chain of value with limited physical and financial resources, resulting in cost savings and improved product quality. As a result of complete utilization of current attributes, acquisition of expense tech, sensible resource planning, and simplified design, a company will benefit from facility efficiency (Jayabalan *et al.*, 2021).

Simmons Koang (2014) asserts that one of the most key factors in determining lower or higher internal efficiency is school organization and structure, and that school-based conditions involve educational facilities and teacher quality. This indicates that the efficiency with which such facilities are used and the quality of the facilities provided to the school will certainly influence the level of the outputs. And since proper instruction cannot occur without sufficient instruments, which are critical in fostering favorable environment in academic settings for both teachers and students. As said by Abdulkareem and Fasasi (2013)'s facility management approach, preparing, staffing, orchestrating, directing, and monitoring the procedures of production, maintenance, consumption, and development of educational establishments are essential roles of school administration in terms of facility management (Souck&Nji, 2017).

D. User knowledge of School Facilities

In a higher learning institution, facilities and their systems provide users with an enhanced learning and instruction environment. As a result, it exposes faculty members and students to new information while also discovering new teaching and learning strategies and untraditional learning activities. A teacher with a positive mindset and good competencies in using facilities and equipment, as well as its applications, should undergo additional training for its beneficial use in learning and teaching activities. In this regard, teachers must be prepared to make the most of the opportunities given in the field of education (Bachalapur&Manjunatha, 2022).

This is why identifying requirements of the users is one of the most difficult challenges for higher education facilities managers (Kamarazaly et al., 2013). POE is a process for gathering user feedback on facility performance in order to improve existing facilities and influence future construction and design. POE can be used to collect feedback on energy efficiency, indoor environment quality, and user satisfaction, among other things. The experiences are drawn from facility users' perceived satisfaction. In this context, satisfaction refers to a comparison of the manageable performance experienced by users as expected from a facility's performance (Baird and Dykes, 2012; David Jiboye, 2012). In these situations, user perception of how the facilities' performance attributes support their academic pursuits and well-being is reflected in how satisfied users are with an educational setting. According to Seshadhri and Paul (2017), satisfaction is the complementing endorsement of users' contentment. In actuality, these performance metrics ought to assess how well the facility satisfies user expectations and needs (Douglas, 1996) (Abisuga, Wang, &Sunindijo, 2019).

One of a university's primary strategic components that it also depends on is its students. In a cutthroat environment, it's critical to satisfy them in order to lure in more students for upcoming programs (Tinapay et al., 2022). Students' satisfaction is a momentary emotion that results from an assessment of academic experience, services, and resource a student employs while learning (Elliott and Shin, 2002; Weerasinghe and Dedunu, 2017; Weerasinghe and Fernando, 2017). If students have a knowledge on how to use the resources their learning will be facilitated. As a result, universities can use understanding about just how student satisfaction develops to create strategies that will make them more appealing to prospective students (Weerasinghe, Fernando, & Roberts, 2018).

Without a purpose, information can be regarded as knowledge. It can only help people answer 'who, where, when, what and, and how' questions, whereas knowledge can help people answer 'how-to' questions (Ackoff, 1989). Thus, knowledge is created from information through the process of learning (Bednar, Cunningham, Duffy, & Perry, 1992; Merrill, 1991; Resnick, 1989). In this way, user representations inform design decision-making for improved performance (Hyysalo, 2006b; Sharrock & Anderson, 1994). Designers construct the user experience

based on their own interaction (e.g., their engagement with the relic, their experience as a user) and professional experience (e.g., knowledge gained from inventing the same or similar artifacts) (Oudshoorn& Pinch, 2003;Hyysalo, 2006a). These imply that users' knowledge will be rooted on how the learning is created in pertaining to the user's information and process (Oygür, 2018).

E. Resources and Equipment of School Facilities

The Association of Career and Technical Education (2009) posits that a skilled workforce and well-educated is the foundation of business growth and innovation, as well as setting individuals and communities on the path of self-sufficiency. As stated by Furfuri and Muhammad (in Chukwuji, Nwankwo, Tsafe, Sayudi& Yusuf, 2017) that it facilitates access to teaching resources and provides the children the opportunities to acquire 21st-century learning skills. It suffices therefore to say that the educational system and its products (students) depend on the adequacy of facilities and equipment with various resources to achieve set academic goals not just on the pro vision. Example of these resources and equipment includes stainless tables, high chairs/ bar chairs, dish rack/cabinets utensils, kitchen furniture and tools, walk-in oven, computers, and various machines that aid in the processing, storage, and easy access. Without the purchasing of this equipment, tools affect the achievement of set educational goals (Chukwuji, 2020).

Ample equipment and tools are critical in preparing students for a growing 21st-century workforce. Inadequate teaching materials have been written about throughout the educational system, and such deficiencies may leave gaps in students' ability to become proficient in this challenging service industry. Programs should ensure that adequate equipment and tools are available to meet curriculum content and industry standards. It is also recommended to investigate purchasing decisions for laboratory tools. Ineffective teachers, as a result of a lack of adequate training (Darling-Hammond, 2000), as well as a scarcity of appropriate teaching materials, can indeed be disadvantageous to the educational process (Darling-Hammond, 2007). The scarcity of obtainable resources and equipment can be caused by a variety of factors, and it can be a significant source of concern for interested parties and stakeholders. Teachers frequently encounter additional difficulties due to a lack of adequate teaching resources, the constant change in standards and objectives, and problems connected to lecturing self-efficacy and resource availability. Doerfert (2011) asserts that having access to sufficient resources is a requirement for delivering high-quality training. Students' capacity to acquire relevant abilities is constrained without sufficient teaching resources, and the effectiveness of instruction may also suffer (McCubbins, et.al., 2016).

According to Farombi (1998), teaching materials are including books, audio-visual, computer, and components of educational technology. He also stated that the accessibility, proficiency, and applicability of teaching materials in classrooms can impact quality teaching by having a positive impact on students' learning and

academic performance. According to Oni (1992), teaching materials are a strategic factor for teachers in providing and organizing education because they help to illustrate a concept that the instructor could not clearly perform without instructional material. According to these researchers, the accessibility of educational resources can be most effective if other criteria are met, such as the facility's quality and the ability of instructors to utilize these resources. In addition, both teachers and students cannot perform the task gracefully without adequate resources and equipment. This is so, teachers or students drive to buy their own for them to use (Tety, 2016).

F. Level of School Instructions

The most documented theme among the selected research was "teaching and learning," with a wide range of focal points (by retrieval frequency). Educators have kept up with modern technology and pedagogy in terms with using approaches and tools to enhance learning and teaching. Students' perceptions of digital learning tools (Ali et al., 2014) as well as perception styles of learning in virtual classroom settings (Hsu, 2011) have been studied by researchers. Zahra (2012) examined how learning journals can be used to improve authentic learning. Cumming (2010) found that student-initiated group management techniques improved learning and group work experience. According to Miller et al. (2012), students have a generally positive attitude to the use of "classroom response system" technology in achieving learning results through active interaction.

Furthermore, Penfold and van der Veen (2014) examined the learning methods of Confucian lineage culture students and discovered that the majority of learners supported deep learning, which contrasted sharply with the teachers' points of view on students embracing surface learning. Style of learning and student choice have emerged as a significant theme, with several studies acknowledging style of learning and students' learning preference in combination with teaching methods (Maumbe, 2014), learning techniques (Jongh and Murphy, 2011), teaching strategies and techniques (Brown et al., 2013), and effective teaching or excellence evaluation (Weber et al., 2010). Johanson and Haug (2008) examined first-, second-, and third-year students' learning style preferences and noted that learning styles can change and that curriculum content should be adjusted for practitioner-oriented versus theorist learners. Cranage et al. (2006) found a correlation among active, sensing, spatial, and sequenced learning styles in a survey of undergraduates, implying that learning style influences study preference. The most documented theme among the selected research was "teaching and learning," with a variety of focal points (by retrieval frequency). Educators have kept up with modern technology and pedagogy in terms of using approaches and tools to enhance learning and teaching.

Rosenshine (1979) discovered that effective teachers include an instructional sequence known as direct instruction in their lessons. Direct instruction is distinguished by starting the lesson with a brief statement of goals, reviewing learning, displaying new content in

small steps, letting learners practice time after each step, providing detailed and clear directions or explanations, parties involved and ample training, asking questions, testing students' skills and talents and checking for understanding, and gaining responses from all students (Tirol, 2021). It reiterated that these measures are particularly appropriate when the substance is unique, challenging, or hierarchies, or even when students are fresh or having difficulty learning. The categories are found in the literature on the relevance of instruction: concise instruction with clearly defined goals, well-structured classes, activating colleges, and, where necessary, 'direct' instruction is integrated (van de Grift, 2007).

Educators have kept up with the latest technology and pedagogy in aspects through using approaches and tools to enhance classroom instruction and learning. Researchers investigated students' perceptions of digital learning tools and conceptual styles of learning in the virtual classroom setting (Ali et al., 2014). (Hsu, 2011). Zahra (2012) examined how learning journals can be used to improve authentic learning. Cumming (2010) found that student-initiated team management strategies learning experience and team work experience. According to Miller et al. (2012), students have a generally positive attitude toward the use of "classroom response system" innovation in attaining learning results through interactive engagement. Furthermore, van der Veen and Penfold(2014) examined the learning outcomes of Confucian historic culture students and discovered that the majority of learners grasped deep learning, which was in stark contrast to the teachers' viewpoints on students embracing surface learning. In addition, instruction is a vital component of learning it has a great effect if it is not taught well by the provider, while learning styles, interests, and pedagogical approaches differ, a similarity or remarkable fad is for learning and teaching to regress from its traditional means of convention, framework, and isolation to one characterized by relations and student-centeredness, learning in recreation (or learning as fun), learning as an immersive experience, and the cultivating of cultures of learning and practice are components of instructions (Hsu, Xiao, & Chen, 2017).

Studies have shown students prefer active learning advancement or progress (e.g. Arcodia & Barron, 2002; Green & Sammons, 2014). While both teacher-centered and learner-centered approaches to learning have advantages, learner-centered techniques focus on the learner rather than the teacher and pay attention not only to the content delivery, which is common in college classrooms, but also to what learners can do (Weimer, 2002). Flexing the scholars' abilities is giving them an opportunity to explore their knowledge and enhance their skills to some extent (Deale, 2019).

Lin (2002) proposed that hospitality educators should encourage industry professionals to help them in continuously modernize curricula in order for institutions to meet industry demands. Online learning is part of the curriculum update. The collaborative effort between hospitality organizations and industry experts will serve as

a resource for students to learn about industry competencies. To keep their curriculum current, hospitality educators must customize it to satisfy the demands of the industry. It is critical that industry input into curriculum development is continuous, current, and relevant (Arendt & Ravinchandran, 2008). In a study conducted by Lashley (1999), the knowledge and skills of HRM students in British, Australia, and Asia were revealed. The majority of learners in a British and an Australian HRM program demonstrated styles of learning that enjoyed the practical activity. Singaporean hospitality students, on the other hand, preferred to learn through assessment and reasoning before acting. These students find it difficult to study case studies because they require a lot of information and time to complete a task. Learning varies the preferences of students on how to learn and teachers on how to teach (Nair & George, 2016).

G. Teachers' Quality

Teacher quality matters in every aspect of instruction. It is, in fact, the most influential school-related factor which influences student achievement. This contains five broad categories of quantifiable and policy-relevant indicators used to organize the teacher qualities posited to reflect teacher quality. The first is teaching experience; studies have found that experience has a positive effect on teacher effectiveness, particularly during the initial years of teaching. Second, programs for teacher preparation and degrees have a positive impact on student achievement, which may be a reflection of the teacher's cognitive ability. Evidence suggests that advanced degree-holding teachers have a positive effect on their students' achievement when those degrees are in related subjects. The third factor is teacher certification; research has shown that certified teachers have a positive effect on HTP program success when the credential is required. It has been demonstrated that emergency or alternate solution certification has little discernible impact on student performance when likened to teachers who obtain standard certification. Fourth, teacher preparation in both subject matter and instructional practices contributes to favorable educational outcomes (Comediero et al., 2022). Pedagogical coursework appears to improve teacher quality at all levels, especially when combined with content knowledge. The significance of information coursework is most pronounced; they suggest positive impact in terms of opportunities to learn the profession and stress reduction among new teachers. The final category includes the teachers' own test results. Teacher literacy or verbal ability tests have been linked to a higher level of student outcomes. The NTE and other government exams of teaching abilities and/or basic skills have been shown to be less reliable indicators of teacher performance.

Teachers have a huge impact on outcomes of student learning and school performance as the strongest school-related factor. Among the factors under the direct authority of school systems, educators provide the biggest opportunity for students to improve their quality of life. According to *How the World's Finest Performing School Systems Rise to the Top*, a global study showing data from the OECD's International Student Assessment Program.

“The quality of an education system cannot exceed the quality of its teachers” (Barber and Mourshed, 2007: p. iii). According to the research that “while schools have powerful effects on student achievement differences, these effects appear to derive most importantly from variations in teacher quality” (Hanushek et al., 1998: p. 1). Teachers who have the same educational background and resources must do things differently in their classrooms, allowing their students to excel at different levels. To understand what makes an instructor effective, one must look inside the classroom's black box and observe how lecturers translate their subject knowledge, pedagogical practices, and materials into advantages for student learning. This is to evaluate that they learn something (Stronge, Grant, & Xu, 2015).

H. Teachers' Methods and Activities

HTP instructors should consider context and, relying on this, combine a variety of teaching methods that provide learners with a broad scope of skills required and up-to-date knowhow of the entrepreneurship activities. One of the most pressing concerns is how the topic should be supposed to teach. Educators continue to struggle to identify appropriate educational objectives, and little is known about effective HTP teaching techniques (Pittaway & Cope, 2006) (Brockhaus, Hills, Klandt, & Welsch, 2001). According to (Mwasalwiba, 2010), the current HTP pedagogy should be primarily revised in order to establish a successful and effective learning and teaching strategy (Mwasalwiba, 2010). It necessitates the development of an integrated teaching and learning strategy that conforms intended results with effective pedagogy selection. In the learning process, efficient method, competent instructors, and adequate teaching facilities are critical. Given that HT scholars have reached an agreement that entrepreneurship can be taught (Ismail, 2010), the focus has shifted on what should be instructed and what should be imparted (Chief Scientist, 2015, Fayolle, 2007, Lourenco, and Jones, 2006). The main teaching methods will be evaluated, and the efficiency of the particular teaching techniques to produce a competitive individual with regards to HTP at the university/college level will be discussed (Ahmad, Abu Bakar, & Ahmad, 2018).

Scientific knowledge development can take various forms (knowledge enrichment, knowledge integration, and theory transformation), and scientific practices and knowledge can be integrated in various methods (Tirol, 2022). They advocate for more opportunities for professional development for teachers to learn how to utilize LP methods to produce LPs and materials needed that are tailored to their own classroom teaching, rather than just how to use study LPs in the classroom (Jin, et.al., 2019).

A teaching strategy that effectively increases the effectiveness of learning is learning through experience. Additionally, Kolb (1984) suggests that practice is how people learn and gain knowledge, or how experience becomes knowledge. According to some researchers (e.g., Horng et al., 2020; Keegan, Losardo, & McCullough, 2017), the use of experiential teaching techniques, such as

civic engagement, has boosted students' awareness of their values and social duty across a range of undergraduate fields. According to Guachalla and Gledhill (2019), when teachers incorporate experiential learning into their curriculum design, it helps students acquire the necessary professional skills for the tourism industry. These skills include the ability to write an effective autobiography and resume, perform well in job interviews, have strong learning capacities, and complete psychological assessments that gauge psychological traits and other dimensional factors. El Hanandeh (2016) also makes the case that field trips give students opportunities to learn things like teamwork and interpersonal skills of communication in the context of actual social events. This kind of engaged learning experience could offer strategies and tactics for hands-on instructional methods (Rong-Da Liang, 2021).

I. School Instructions Assessment

Different sources' assessments of an instructor's teaching effectiveness represent different observation or perceptions. The response of students and teachers' identity usually display teaching problems. Aditya, Chiranjib, and Souvik (2009) pointed out that the assessment of student ratings for increasing the quality of higher education had already been well investigated. A questionnaire for evaluation was further designed by Spooren, Mortelmans, and Denekens (2007) so that students may express their experiences with and appreciation for the teachings they learned from their professors and teaching assistants. It's quite complicated to determine the possible reasons of instructional deficits in an objective manner. The result of the student evaluations can assist teachers in devising instructional strategies which will help in student learning. The quickest source of information for measuring teaching performance is instructor self-ratings. The assessment provides an opportunity to assess teaching effectiveness and highlight the needs of students. Faculty members, however, may not be credible judges of student readiness outside of their field of expertise as they might not have actual knowledge about the syllabus outside of their teaching emphasis (Yu & Ueng, 2012).

The teacher's assessment method often fails of the stated goals or objectives, and as an outcome, the teacher is not assessing what they ought to be after the class (Comedieroet al., 2022). The assessment should meet the set goals. A valid and reliable learning assessment tool is also weighed to assure that the objectives were able to achieve (Estacio, 2012).

Self-assessment is also known as Assessment as Learning (AAL). It develops personal responsibility for learning in the learner (Corpuz, 2012, p. 5). It is an essential component in metacognition that promotes active learning. It occurs when students reflect on, and evaluate their own work (Rosaroso, 2016, p. 89), their own strengths and weaknesses (Pidor, 2012, p. 57), chart the attainment of learning outcomes, and regulate their learning progress that shapes their future dreams. It develops the learner to be self-directed and independent in learning (Corpuz, p. 5). To assist their involvement and learning activities that

facilitate learning performance the students must engage in a reflection on what kind of learning works and what needs improvement they may have (National Research Council, 2001, p. 12). This includes the use of checklists, rating scales, anecdotal records, self-reports, and other forms of psychometrics to accomplish the learning outcomes (Inocian, 2018).

J. Teacher Performance

The teacher's performance can be widely classified into three main categories, i.e. Task performance, contextual performance, and contextual performance are all factors to consider (Bakker & Bal, 2010; Cai & Lin, 2006; Carson, 2006; Min, 2007). Job performance refers to a set of behavior patterns that an employee demonstrates when he or she comprehends and acknowledges that the goals of the organization have been investigated and highlighted. It is actually activities involved in the employee's job and also the technical behavior (Griffin, Neal & Neale, 2000). From that, the employee's proficiency in performing technical tasks is actually checked (Borman & Brush, 1993). In the area of teaching, task performance entails a set of governed job behaviors that a teacher can engage in. The task performance of teachers includes teacher-student contact, teaching quality, and teacher performance (Khan et al., 2012).

Quality and effective teachers can be very influential on student performance. Importance of teachers cannot be overseeing as they can directly influence student achievement. Teacher effectiveness and its quality relates to SES because students of low SES, low achievement, and minority status are less likely to be exposed to highly qualified, effective teachers (Lankford et al., 2002). This is due, in part of, to the tendency for more qualified teachers to eventually seek employment in schools that have high-achieving students, greater resources, and strong administrative support (Hanushek et al., 2004; Rumberger and Palardy, 2005). Research investigating the effects of teacher quality on academic performance has demonstrated that having access to highly qualified teachers can have a significant impact on student achievement (Carlisle & Murray, 2015).

Teachers play a crucial role in providing education to students. Every school strives to recruit good and qualified teaching personnel that can deliver quality education to its students. Only highly qualified and committed teaching staff, personnel or teachers can produce effective results by producing good-quality students, who can give a contribution to their country in the future. Therefore, it is vital for schools to keep talented or key teaching staff because only qualified teachers can give the best education to the students. Thus, for the quality of education, the quality of teachers matters a lot. But if the qualified teachers are leaving intentions from the school or teaching field, then it will have a negative impact on students and the school's performance as well. Thus, it is very essential to keep highly qualified teachers to deliver a good quality education. Teachers' performance cannot be ignored in this matter (Tehseen & Ul Hadi, 2015).

Evaluating faculty performance is one of the measures of higher education institutions to determine the quality of the delivery of instruction and student services inside the classroom. Maintaining quality instruction is the intention and goal of every higher education institution to meet the challenges and demands of internationalization. In the implementation of the curriculum, teachers play an important role. No matter how excellent the design of the curriculum, if it will not be delivered to the students proficiently, the goal of achieving Outcomes-based Education would never be realized and accomplished successfully. Training of faculty members serves as an important aspect of human resource management in higher education institutions that seeks to develop the competence of the teachers in delivering quality instruction and services to students to ensure quality (An, Laguador, & Portugal, 2015). According to (Bay, An, & Laguador, 2014) teachers must always be updated on the latest or current trends and issues concerning their field of specialization to keep their students well informed on the situations of the corporate world (Laguador, Deligero, & Cueto, 2015).

K. School Achievements of Instruction

It is acknowledged as obvious that teachers are of major importance in the creation of a quality and successful education, the development of students, and in student achievement at school (Barber & Mourshed, 2007; OECD, 2005, 2010b). The first McKinsey report undoubtedly concludes that (1) the educational system is only as good as the teachers constituting it; (2) successful learning cannot be imagined without quality teaching; (3) for excellent performance the success of every child is a prerequisite (Barber & Mourshed, 2007). Thus, achievements may refer to teachers' achievements and performance, and students' achievements and accomplishments contribute to one another. The importance must be shown to everyone to indicate accomplishments (Széll, 2013).

Teacher effectiveness encompasses factors that reach beyond the classroom such as teacher behavior and expectations, pre-existing teacher characteristics, teacher training, and external and internal teaching contexts. In addition, research suggests that teacher effectiveness is also derived from the consistency of teachers' effects in the classroom, in terms of time stability, subject consistency, differentiated roles, and types of the student (Ko & Sammons, 2012). At the classroom level, overall teaching quality and expectations are most relevant, while curriculum coverage, instructional approaches, and the provision of good-quality feedback to students are relevant to addressing the educational needs of so-called lower achievers (Mincu, 2015).

III. CONCLUSION

Since in this 21st-century outcome-based is integrated, teachers will have based on the outcome of students that exhibit their performance. If the institution is inadequate to produce quality students for the program, there will be a scarcity of tools and equipment for the instructional materials. Lastly, students who participated in competitions with the assistance of teachers and coaches

must be equipped in terms of knowledge and skills, this is to determine the competitiveness of students. Receiving awards from the participating competition determine the competitiveness of the teacher and the school. This is to support that facilities and instructions in school are correlated that contribute to students' achievements. Though efficiency indicates how well an organization has used its resources to produce the best outcome over a period, these outcomes may either be defined in terms of intermediate outputs such as the number of accomplishments received by the students and teachers as well as the awards which refer to achievements. The most critical aspect of educational institutions offering Hospitality and Tourism programs is reassuring its competitiveness in terms of facilities and instructions. Without those learning is difficult and dire.

REFERENCES

BOOKS

- [1.] Carlisle, B. L., & Murray, C. B. (2015). *Academic Performance, Effects of Socio-Economic Status on. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)*, 43-48.
- [2.] Oygür, I. (2018). *The machineries of user knowledge. Design Studies*, 23-49.
- [3.] Stronge, J. H., Grant, L. W., & Xu, X. (2015). *Teacher Behaviours and Student Outcomes. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)*, 44-50

CONGRESS PROCEEDINGS

- [4.] Perman, L., & Mikinac, K. (2014). EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION PROCESSES IN TOURISM. *Tourism and Hospitality Industry 2014, CONGRESS PROCEEDINGS* (pp. 616-617). *Croatia: Tourism and Hospitality Industry 2014, CONGRESS PROCEEDINGS*.

JOURNALS/ARTICLES

- [5.] Abdullahi, I., Wan, Z., & Wan, Y. (2018). Effect of the performance of physical and non-physical facilities on higher institutional facilities. *Journal of Facilities Management*, 8-41.
- [6.] Abisuga, A. O., Wang, C. C., & Sunindijo, R. Y. (2019). A holistic framework with user-centred facilities performance attributes for evaluating higher education buildings. *Facilities*, 132-160.
- [7.] Ahmad, S. Z., Abu Bakar, A. R., & Ahmad, N. (2018). An evaluation of teaching methods of entrepreneurship in hospitality and tourism programs. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 14-25.
- [8.] Assante, L. M., Huffman, L., & Harp, S. S. (2010). A Taxonomy of Academic Quality Indicators for U.S.-Based 4-Year Undergraduate Hospitality Management Programs. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 164-184.
- [9.] Babalola, T. K., & Moodley, I. (2020). Babalola, Tesleem K.; Moodley, Indres (2020). Assessing the Efficiency of Health-care Facilities in Sub-Saharan

- Africa: A Systematic Review. *Health Services Research and Managerial Epidemiology*, 1-12.
- [10.] Bachalapur, M. M., & Manjunatha, S. (2022). ICT Competence and Attitude among Faculty members related Review of Literature from the period 2012-2021. *Scholarly Journal*, 1-15.
- [11.] Bowers, A. J., & Urick, A. (2011). Does High School Facility Quality Affect Student Achievement? A Two-Level Hierarchical Linear Model. *Journal of Education Finance*, 72-94.
- [12.] Chukwuji, C. N. (2020). An Assessment Of The Level Of Provision Of Library Space And Equipment Among Secondary Schools In Gusau Towards Achieving Educational Goals . *MBJLIS – Middlebelt Journal of Library and Information Science*,, 90-102.
- [13.] Comediero, P. B., Tinapay, A. O., Samillano, J. H., & Tirol, S. L. (2022). Teaching and Assessment Practices in Mathematics in the Spiral Progression of the K to 12 Curriculum. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Volume 7, Issue 10, 1817-1825.
- [14.] Deale, C. S. (2019). Learning Preferences Instead of Learning Styles:A Case Study of Hospitality Management Students' Perceptions of How They Learn Best and Implications for Teaching and Learning. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 1-7.
- [15.] Abdullahi, I., Wan, Z., & Wan, Y. (2018). Effect of the performance of physical and non-physical facilities on higher institutional facilities. *Journal of Facilities Management*, 8-41.
- [16.] Abisuga, A. O., Wang, C. C., & Sunindijo, R. Y. (2019). A holistic framework with user-centred facilities performance attributes for evaluating higher education buildings. *Facilities*, 132-160.
- [17.] Ahmad, S. Z., Abu Bakar, A. R., & Ahmad, N. (2018). An evaluation of teaching methods of entrepreneurship in hospitality and tourism programs. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 14-25.
- [18.] Assante, L. M., Huffman, L., & Harp, S. S. (2010). A Taxonomy of Academic Quality Indicators for U.S.-Based 4-Year Undergraduate Hospitality Management Programs. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 164-184.
- [19.] Babalola, T. K., & Moodley, I. (2020). Babalola, Tesleem K.; Moodley, Indres (2020). Assessing the Efficiency of Health-care Facilities in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review. *Health Services Research and Managerial Epidemiology*, 1-12.
- [20.] Bachalapur, M. M., & Manjunatha, S. (2022). ICT Competence and Attitude among Faculty members related Review of Literature from the period 2012-2021. *Scholarly Journal*, 1-15.
- [21.] Bowers, A. J., & Urick, A. (2011). Does High School Facility Quality Affect Student Achievement? A Two-Level Hierarchical Linear Model. *Journal of Education Finance*, 72-94.
- [22.] Chukwuji, C. N. (2020). An Assessment Of The Level Of Provision Of Library Space And Equipment Among Secondary Schools In Gusau Towards Achieving Educational Goals . *MBJLIS – Middlebelt Journal of Library and Information Science*,, 90-102.
- [23.] Comediero, P. B., Tinapay, A. O., Samillano, J. H., & Tirol, S. L. (2022). Teaching and Assessment Practices in Mathematics in the Spiral Progression of the K to 12 Curriculum. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Volume 7, Issue 10, 1817-1825.
- [24.] Deale, C. S. (2019). Learning Preferences Instead of Learning Styles:A Case Study of Hospitality Management Students' Perceptions of How They Learn Best and Implications for Teaching and Learning. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 1-7.
- [25.] Earthman, G. I. (2002). School Facility Conditions and Student Academic Achievement. *UCLA's Institute for Democracy, Education, & Access*, 8-10.
- [26.] Goh, E. (2011). The Value and Benefits of Fieldtrips in Tourism and Hospitality Education . *Higher Learning Communications Research Journal*, 60-70.
- [27.] Hsu, C. H., Xiao, H., & Chen, N. (2017). Hospitality and tourism education research from 2005 to 2014: "Is the past a prologue to the future?". *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 141-160.
- [28.] Imran, R. (2010). Students' Perceptions of Effectiveness of Hospitality Curricula and Their Preparedness. *ScholarWorks*, 3-80.
- [29.] Jin, H., Mikeska, J. N., Hokayem, H., & Mavronikolas, E. (2019). Toward coherence in curriculum, instruction, and assessment: A review of learning progression literature. *Science Education*, 3-27.
- [30.] Khan, Anwar; Mad Shah, Ishak; Khan, Sadaf; Gul, Shafiq. (2012). Teachers' stress, performance & resources The Moderating effects of resources on stress & performance. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 10-23.
- [31.] Laguador, J. M., Deligero, J. C., & Cueto, A. (2015). Students' Evaluation On The Teaching Performance Of Tourism And Hospitality Management Faculty Members. *Asian Journal of Educational Research* , 1-6.
- [32.] Lam, T., & Xiao, H. (2000). Challenges and constraints of hospitality and tourism education in China. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 291-295.
- [33.] Lyimo, N. S., Too, J. K., & Kipng'etich, K. J. (2017). Perception of teachers on availability of instructional materials and physical facilities in secondary schools of Arusha District, Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 103-112.
- [34.] Lyimo, N. S., Too, J. K., & Kipng'etich, K. J. (2017). Perception of teachers on availability of instructional materials and physical facilities in secondary schools of Arusha District, Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 103-112.

- [35.] Lyimo, N. S., Too, J. K., & Kipng'etich, K. J. (2017). Perception of Teachers on Availability of Instructional Materials and Physical Facilities in Secondary Schools of Arusha District, Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 103-112.
- [36.] Mainardes, E. W., Ferreira, J. J., & Tontini, G. (2011). Creating a competitive advantage in Higher Education Institutions: proposal and test of a conceptual model. *International Journal of Management in Education*, 5, 145-168.
- [37.] McCubbins, O., Anderson, R. G., Paulsen, T. H., & Wells, T. (2016). Teacher-perceived Adequacy of Tools and Equipment Available to Teach Agricultural Mechanics . *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 223-236.
- [38.] McCubbins, O., Anderson, R. G., Paulsen, T. H., & Wells, T. (2016). Teacher-perceived Adequacy of Tools and Equipment Available to Teach Agricultural Mechanics . *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 223-236.
- [39.] Mincu, M. E. (2015). Teacher quality and school improvement: what is the role of research? . *Oxford Review of Education*, 253-269.
- [40.] Mohammad, B. A., & Alsaleh, H. T. (2013). Motivation of Students to Study Tourism Hospitality Programs. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 1637–1647.
- [41.] Nair, R., & George, B. P. (2016). E-learning adoption in hospitality education: An analysis with special focus on Singapore. *Journal of Tourism, Heritage & Services Marketing*, 3-10.
- [42.] Pajares, F. (2003). Self-Efficacy Beliefs, Motivation, And Achievement In Writing: A Review Of The Literature. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 139-158.
- [43.] Rice, J. K. (2003). *Teacher Quality: Understanding the Effectiveness of Teacher Attributes*. Washington, DC: Economic Policy Institute.
- [44.] Rong-Da Liang, A. (2021). Examining the factors of experiential learning and teaching style: A case study of a hospitality and tourism program . *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education* , 1-10.
- [45.] Shen Huawen, Lou J.M., Lam C.F. (May 31, 2015). Evaluating the Quality of Hospitality and Tourism Education in Vocational Institute in China. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 12.
- [46.] Souck, E. N., & Nji, G. (2017). The Effects of School Facilities on Internal Efficiency: The Case of Selected Bilingual Secondary Schools in Yaounde Centre. *World Journal of Research and Review (WJRR)*, 41-48.
- [47.] SOUCK, E. N., & NJI, G. (2017). The Effects of School Facilities on Internal Efficiency: The Case of Selected Bilingual Secondary Schools in Yaounde Centre . *World Journal of Research and Review*, 41-48.
- [48.] Széll, K. (2013). Factors Determining Student Achievement. *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, 55-66.
- [49.] Tehseen, S., & Ul Hadi, N. (2015). Factors Influencing Teachers' Performance and Retention. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 233-241.
- [50.] Tety, J. L. (2016). Role of instructional materials in academic performance in community secondary schools in Rombo District. *CORE*, 18-80.
- [51.] Tinapay, A.O. & Tirol, S. L. (2022). "Social Cognitive Development on the Implementation of Student Manual in a Higher Education Institution: A Literature Review," *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, Volume: 5 Issue: 4, pp. 54-63, 2022. DOI: 10.51386/25815946/ijms-v5i4p106
- [52.] Tirol, S. L. (2022). "Spiral Progression Approach in The K to 12 Science Curriculum: A Literature Review," *International Journal of Education (IJE) Vol.10, No.4*, December 2022, pp. 29-44. DOI:10.5121/ije.2022.10403
- [53.] Tirol, S. L. (2021). "Spiral Progression of Biology Content in the Philippine K to 12 Science Curriculum," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, Volume 4, Issue 6, pp. 20-27, 2021.
- [54.] van de Grift, W. (2007). Quality of teaching in four European countries: a review of the literature and application of an assessment instrument. *Educational Research*, 127-152.
- [55.] Vidalakis, C., Sun, M., & Papa, A. (2013). The quality and value of higher education facilities: a comparative study. *Emerald Insight*, 489-504.
- [56.] Weerasinghe, S., Fernando, R. L., & Roberts, B. (2018). University facilities and student satisfaction in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 1-30.
- [57.] Ylagan, A. P. (2018). Teaching Performance Of The College Of International Tourism And Hospitality Management. *Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 425-433.
- [58.] Yu, K.-T., & Ueng, R.-G. (2012). Enhancing teaching effectiveness by using the Six-Sigma DMAIC model. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 949-961.

ONLINE SOURCES

- [59.] <https://www.tcrecord.org/Content.asp?ContentId=11852>
- [60.] [http://eprints.utm.my/id/eprint/80501/1/NurulSyaki maMohdYusoff2017_TheDevelopmentoftheKeyPerformanceIndicators.pdf](http://eprints.utm.my/id/eprint/80501/1/NurulSyaki%20maMohdYusoff2017_TheDevelopmentoftheKeyPerformanceIndicators.pdf)